

P. M. HEGDE & CO.

CHARTERED ACCOUNTANTS

1st Floor, 'Manasa Towers', M.G. Road,
Kodialball, MANGALORE - 575 003.

Partners :

H. R. SHETTY, B.Com., LL.B., F.C.A.

S. DAYASHARAN SHETTY, B.Com., F.C.A.

INTERNSHIP CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Ms. **Mohammed Jasim Jalal Kottikulam**, Reg.No.2SU19AC010 student of B.com (Professional with ACCA) at Srinivas College of Management & Commerce, Mangaluru, has completed his internship in our organization. He worked as an intern from **01-10-2021 to 11-12-2021**. He has shown keen interest and actively involved in all the tasks assigned to him. He discharged the responsibilities to the satisfaction of his fellow workers and supervisors. His conduct and character were good during the period of internship.

We wish him every success in his future endeavour.

Evaluation Parameters	Marks Scored
1. Interns Initial Learning Objective	20
2.Attendence & Time management Throughout Internship	16
3.Interns Work Capacity & Behaviour	20
4. Interns Growth and Development During Internship	20
5. Internship Summary Report	18
Total Marks	94

Place : Mangalore

Date : 11-12-2021

For P.M. HEGDE & CO.,
Chartered Accountants
FRN/001/16S

(DAYASHARAN SHETTY)
Partner
Membership No. 203107

COLLEGE CERTIFICATE

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(PRIVATE UNIVERSITY ESTABLISHED UNDER KARNATAKA STATE ACT NO 42 OF 2013)

City Office: G.H.B. Road, MANGALURU - 575 001, Karnataka State, INDIA.

Phone No.: 0824 2428966, 2444891, Fax: 0824-2442766

E-mail: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in website: www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Ref No. SUB/COM/Int/2021

DI: 23.08.2021

To Whomsoever It May Concern

Sub : Request for Permission to carry out Internship Training - reg.

Greetings from College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore.

We are glad to inform you that we are offering a B. Com (Professional with ACCA) UG Degree Course approved by Government of Karnataka.

As a part of our curriculum and in order to make education more meaningful, our students are supposed to get practical exposure to real life business operations. In this connection, Mrs. HANAN BASHEER (Reg. No. 2SU19AC007), a student of Final year (VI Semester) B. Com. (Professional with ACCA) UG Degree course is interested to carry out Internship training in your esteemed organization and understand the managerial practices of your concern.

Hence, we request you permit the above mentioned student to carry out project training in your esteemed organization. We assure you that the information furnished will be used for academic purpose only.

Your co-operation and help in this regard will be highly appreciated.

Thanking you,

Yours faithfully,

Dean

DEAN

College of Management & Commerce
Srinivas University
Mangalore - 575 001

K. ASHOK RAO & CO.
CHARTERED ACCOUNTANTS

D.No. 24-20-1617/11, Second Floor,
"SANRITA BUILDING",
Marnamikatta, Mangalore - 575 001

Tel./Fax : (0824) 2419739 (O)
Mob : 9448327527
Email : kashokrao7@rediffmail.com

Date: 09.12.2021

Ref. No.

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Ms. AMRITA DSOUZA**, D/O Timothy Dsouza, residing at Classique Gateway, Kankanady Bypass Road, Near Ganesh Medicals, Kankanady, Mangalore has undergone internship training programme at my office for a period from 9th September 2021 to 9th December 2021 . During the tenure of her service in my office I found her very honest, obedient and hardworking. I wish her all the success in her future endeavors.

SIGNATURE

TO WHOMSOEVER IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that Mr. MUHAMMED SALMAN MARZOOK, a student of final year (V Semester) B.Com (Professional with ACCA) UG Degree Course during the academic year 2021-22 of 'Srinivas University' had undertaken Internship Programme in my office from 1st September 2021 to 15th December, 2021 as a part of their academic curriculum.

I wish him the very best in his future endeavours.

PLACE: MANGALORE**DATE : 15.12.2021****ABDUL SAMAD B.Com., F.C.A.
CHARTERED ACCOUNTANT
(M.No.200568)**

مشاريح ام. اتش. ذ.م.م.
M.H. ENTERPRISES L.L.C.

Experience Certificate

This is to certify that **Mr. Baasim Hassan, S/o Mohammed Shafeequ** has served as an Internship Trainee at **M.H. Enterprises.LLC** from the period of **3rd September 2021 to 5th January 2022** in finance department.

During his employment, he has pursued knowledge and experience in the areas of Accounting, Auditing, Taxation (Vat & Excise tax) and related computer skills from our organization.

He has proved himself and has been very hardworking and dedicated. We have noticed that with his timeliness and dedication, projects went very well on time. He can be named among those who deserve excellent growth in Accounts career.

Please feel free to contact us if you have specific questions regarding his employment.

We wish him all success in all his future efforts.

DATE: 06/01/2022

PLACE: AL-QUOZ (DUBAI, UAE)

FOR M.H. Enterprises L.L.C
(Parth Pandya)

